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The Influence of Influencer Marketing, Online Customer Review and Online Customer Rating to Purchasing Interest on the Tik Tok Shop Application

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Abstract

Along with the Tik Tok Popularity, there has been TikTok Shop Application that enables the users to buy product directly from Tik Tok platform. The aims of this research are to analyze the influence of influencer marketing, online customer review and online customer rating to the buying interest, and to analyze simultaneously to the influencer marketing, online customer review, and online customer rating to the purchasing interest. The method applied of this research is Multiple linear regression analysis. The data of this research are primary data, while the test stages carried out are: validity, reliability, normality, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, coefficient of determination, f test, and t test. The research data collection used a questionnaire instrument, and the valid data collected were 150 respondents. The sampling method in this study is non-probability sampling with purposive sampling technique. The results showed that the variables of influencer marketing, online customer review, and online customer rating had an effect on purchasing interest. Simultaneously, the variables of influencer marketing, online customer review, and online customer rating have an effect on purchasing interest in the TikTok Shop application.

Keywords: Influencer Marketing, Online Customer Review, Online Customer Rating

1. Introduction

In this digital era nowadays, social media has become an integrated part of many people's daily lives. Social media platforms like TikTok have experienced rapid growth and become popular places for people to share creative content, entertainment, and interact with other users. Along with TikTok's popularity, there has been the TikTok Shop application, which allows users to buy products directly from the TikTok platform.

In an effort to promote and market the products available on Tik Tok Shop, the use of influencer marketing and online consumer reviews is becoming an increasingly common strategy. Influencer marketing involves TikTok users who have a large follower base and significant influence to promote products and brands to their followers.

Meanwhile, online consumer reviews and product ratings also play an important role in creating consumers' perceptions and purchase intention towards the product.

Based on Figure 1, it shows that the survey conducted by the Populix team, 86 percent of respondents have shopped social commerce. The most widely used platform is TikTok Shop (45 percent), followed by WhatsApp (21 percent), Facebook Shop (10 percent), and Instagram Shop (10 percent). TikTok Shop is mostly used by women. While men, especially those aged 36-45 years. Populix wrote, in the future time, women aged 18-25 years will continue to dominate TikTok Shop users.

One of the previous studies conducted by Waluyo and Trishananto (2022), showed that influencers have a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. This means that Shopee users' buying interest is influenced by an influencer. According to Kotler, Kevin, and Chernev (2021, p. 81), influencer marketing is a person who offers informal advice or information about a particular product or product category, such as which brand is best or how a particular product can be used. The influence of individuals or groups who are considered experienced in a field can be an important factor in creating consumer behavior. In the context of TikTok Shop, if an influencer recommends a certain product, consumers tend to feel more confident and interested in buying the product. This can influence consumer purchase intention in the TikTok Shop application.

Figure 1: Social Media Commerce in Indonesia

Source: Rian and Kevin, *KumparanTECH on Populix (kumparan.com) 2022*

Online consumer reviews play an important role in creating consumer perceptions and purchase intention. According to Kotler et al. (2021, p. 92), consumers tend to search information and recommendations from others before making a purchase decision. Positive online consumer reviews can build trust and increase consumer buying interest in a product or brand. Conversely, negative reviews can reduce consumer buying interest. Therefore, online consumer reviews on the TikTok Shop application can influence user buying interest by providing useful information and providing views on product quality. This is supported by the results of research from Harli, Mutasowifin, and Andrianto, (2021), showing that buying interest comes from online customer reviews and online customer ratings which can influence consumers to buy products.

According to Kotler et al. (2021, p. 104), consumers tend to trust and choose products with high ratings. Good ratings can provide positive signals about product quality and increase consumer buying interest. In previous research conducted by Harli, Mutasowifin, and Andrianto (2021) ratings have a positive and significant effect on buying interest in health products at Shopee during the COVID-19 pandemic, high ratings will further influence consumer purchasing interest. In the TikTok Shop application, high product ratings can build trust and make consumers more motivated to buy the product. In the online shopping process, there are several risks that consumers often face, that they do not have the ability to assess goods or services directly. Consumers rely on the seller's information about the product being sold with a description of the product and product images provided by

the seller by looking for information about reviews provided by other consumers who have purchased the goods or services.

According to Kotler, Kevin and Chernev (2021, p. 108), influencers are people who influence purchasing decisions, often by helping to determine specifications and providing information to evaluate alternatives. In the next explanation, Kotler, Kevin and Chernev (2021, p. 318), the term influencer marketing refers to the use of popular online figures to promote products, services or brands in their social media feeds. Influencer marketing has grown rapidly in recent years into a multi-billion dollar industry. This rapid growth has presented some challenges for marketers. Since more companies realize the value of using influencers to promote their offerings, the demand for influencers has increased, and the price to secure an endorsement has risen many times over to reach over \$100,000 for some top influencers.

In Figure 2, the TikTok users can identify the influencer performing the usage of the advertised product. In the video, it is shown that there is a yellow basket as a TikTok Shop feature that makes it easy for users to see the products being sold. In addition, users can see the rating given ranging from 1 star to 5 stars. With the presence of the review feature, of course, users can consider more before buying the product. The existence of these features can give buyers the confidence to use this TikTok Shop and return to shop online using the TikTok application.

Figure 2: Online Customer Review dan Online Customer Rating

Source: TikTok Shop 2023

The previous research conducted by Waluyo et. al (2022), it was found that influencer marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. In line with the results of research from Agustin and Amron (2022), the influencer marketing has a significant relationship or influence on buying interest. This means that an influencer who has high popularity, credibility, many fans and many followers on social media can make influencers directly determine purchasing decisions.

Harli, Mutasowifin, and Andrianto (2021), show that online consumer reviews have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, because reviews come from the direct experience of previous consumers who bought the product. In Komariyah's research (2022), it shows that ratings have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention for the Shopee online marketplace. With these rating limitations, it still has an influence on consumer purchasing interest, because the rating shows the quality of a product. Similar to the results of research from Mauli and Zulfebriges (2022) and Novihenti and Amin (2022), that online customer ratings have a positive effect on purchase intention.

In the e-marketplace, online customer reviews can greatly influence purchase intention because reviews come from the direct experience of previous consumers who bought the product. A review is one of the main sources of consumers when they want to decide on purchasing interest. Therefore, companies must ask consumers to write the reviews honestly and properly in order to create buying interest for the next consumer (Harli et al., 2021).

According to research by Hasrul, Suharyati and Sembiring (2021); Mawa and Cahyadi (2021), that online customer reviews also have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

A description of the results of previous studies in more detail as follows. Lackermair, Kailer, and Kanmaz (2013) studied the acceptance and use of ratings and reviews in the context of e-commerce transactions. A survey was conducted among 104 online shoppers in Germany to examine how consumer reviews and ratings are used to support purchasing decisions. The survey results show that the reviews and ratings are important sources of information for consumer.

Arif, Mustikowati, and Chrismardani (2023) conducted a study with a quantitative approach. A total of 120 respondents were involved in this study by using convenience sampling techniques in data collection. Multiple linear regression was used to analyze the data. The results of the study show that influencer marketing and online customer reviews have an impact on online purchase decision. Agustin and Amron (2022), analyzed the effect of influencer marketing and price perceptions on interest in buying skincare at TikTok Shop. It was carried out to determine the effect partially or simultaneously using quantitative methods by distributing questionnaires in the form of google forms to 100 people. The samples in this study were TikTok application users who had purchased skincare at TikTok Shop in Semarang City. The technique of data analysis applied is multiple linear analysis and complemented by classical assumption tests in the form of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroschedasticity tests. This study provides information both partially and simultaneously that influencer marketing variables and price perceptions that have a significant relationship or influence on purchase intention.

Amelia, Sakti and Mulyono (2022), analyzed the effect of viral marketing and online customer reviews using TikTok media on buying interest in Scarlett Whitening products. The type of the research used is causal associative research with a quantitative approach. The datum collection method used is a survey method using primary data collected directly from respondents using a questionnaire. The population in this study were all NTB people, with a research sample of 84 people. Sampling using non-probability sampling with purposive sampling technique. The results of the analysis show that viral marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention and online customer reviews also have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

Harli, Mutasowifin and Andrianto (2021), in this study analyzed the effect of online consumer reviews and ratings on buying interest in health products on the Shopee e-marketplace during the COVID-19 pandemic in Jabodetabek. Sample withdrawal was carried out using purposive sampling technique. The methods used in this research are descriptive analysis and SEM-PLS, with 191 respondents. The results of the analysis show that the online consumer review and rating variables have a positive and significant effect on the purchase intention of health products with the rating variable having a more dominant influence.

Komariyah (2022), analyzed the effect of online customer reviews and ratings on Shopee online purchase interest in female santri of the Salafiyah Syafi'iyah Seblak Islamic Boarding School. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 60 respondents. The results of this study state that online customer review and rating each have a significant positive effect on purchase intention. Online customer review and rating together have a significant positive effect on purchase intention seen from the results of the f test which states the F count value of $94.405 > F_{table}$ of 3.16 and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The hypothesis in this study can be accepted, therefore online customer reviews and ratings are included in the important factors that influence purchase intention.

Mauli and Zulfebriges (2022), in their research, analyzed the effect of online customer reviews and Shopee online media ratings on consumer buying interest in the Erigo brand. This study uses multiple linear regression analysis methods, using random sampling techniques. This study took 100 respondents. The results show that online customer Review and Rating have a positive effect on buying interest. Mawa and Cahyadi (2021), using the Snowball Sampling technique so that a sample of 40 respondents was obtained. Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, it shows that price, online customer review and rating have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

Novihenti and Amin (2022), in their research analyzed the effect of online customer reviews, online customer ratings and ease of use of the Shopee online shop application on buying interest. The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. The sample in the study was 130 respondents. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant influence between online customer review and purchase intention. Furthermore, there is a significant influence between online customer rating and ease of use with purchase intention.

Rohmatulloh and Sari (2019), conducted a research to determine the effect of online customer reviews on purchase intention with trust as an intervening variable for Shopee users. This study uses descriptive and causal analysis methods with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) PLS analysis tools. Based on the results of descriptive analysis of online customer review variables, trust and purchase intention are in the very good category. The results of hypothesis testing, online customer review and trust directly have a significant effect on purchase intention, while online customer review on purchase intention through trust, shows a significant indirect effect.

Iffah and Farouk (2022), examined the effect of influencer marketing strategies and online customer reviews on purchase intention in Sociolla users. The scale used in this research questionnaire is a Likert scale. The analysis method used is descriptive analysis, instrument test, classical assumption test, linear regression analysis method, and hypothesis testing. The results of this study indicate that influencer marketing and online customer reviews have a significant effect on purchase intention.

Oryza and Nilowardono (2022), this study, they examined the impact of digital marketing, online customer reviews and ratings on Shopee consumer buying interest. The analysis method used in this research is quantitative analysis by conducting a survey of 106 respondents, namely Narotama University students who have made purchases through shopee. The results of this study indicate that digital marketing, online customer reviews and ratings have a positive effect on buying interest through Shopee. When consumers find Shopee's digital marketing attractive, online customer reviews and other user ratings provide benefits in terms of providing product-related information, this can increase buying interest.

In addition to ratings with star, the users can also first look at the testimonials that other buyers have given. If the product gets a lot of stars of 5 or 4 and positive comments, then it is likely that the product is indeed as expected and as needed. Another facility provided by TikTok Shop is as compensation for discounts if the product obtained is not suitable or damaged, while the money will be returned if the item is not available through notification by the seller.

Various kinds of previous research results that use influencer marketing variables, online customer reviews and online customer ratings, encourage this research to be conducted again. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of influencer marketing, online customer reviews, and online customer ratings on buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. The result of this study can be a reference and source of information so that companies can increase buying interest by paying attention to aspects of influence marketing, online customer review, online customer rating in the future.

Based on the results of previous research studies and supporting theories, the hypothesis of this study is as follows:

- H1: There is an influence between influencer marketing on buying interest in TikTok Shop.
- H2: There is an influence of online customer reviews on buying interest in TikTok Shop.
- H3: There is an influence of online customer rating on buying interest in TikTok Shop.

2. Method

The subjects in this study are TikTok Shop users. The aspects consist of influencer marketing variables (X1), online customer reviews (X2), online customer ratings (X3), and purchase intention (Y). The approach in this study is a quantitative approach, because the data taken during the research can be in the form of numbers and can be analyzed by calculations using statistical methods. The source of information for this research was obtained from the appropriate questionnaire via google form filled in by respondents from TikTok Shop users. This strategy is used to collect information by asking respondents several questions with a survey guide containing questions

related to the Influence of Influencer Marketing, Online Customer Review and Online Customer Rating on Buying Interest in the TikTok Shop application. Sampling according to Hair et al (2018), is used because the population size is uncertain and suggests a minimum sample size of 5-10 multiplied the indicator variable. The number of indicators in this study were 15 times 10 ($15 \times 10 = 150$). So through calculations based on this formula, the number of samples obtained was 150 respondents from TikTok application users.

To measure the ability to influence influencer marketing variables, online customer reviews and online customer ratings on purchase intention, it can be carried out by using Semantic Differential. According to Sugiyono (2019, p. 97), semantic differential is a scale used to measure attitudes, only the form is not multiple choice or checklist, but arranged on a continuum line where the "very positive" answer is located on the right side of the line, and the "very negative" answer is located on the left side of the line, or vice versa. The datum obtained is interval data, and usually this scale is used to measure certain attitudes/characteristics that a person has. Each respondent's answer will be given a value with an interval score of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The respondents can give answers, in the range of positive to negative answers. This depends on the respondent's opinion or perception of each question. Respondents who gave an assessment with a number 5, it meant that the respondent's perception was very positive to the question, if the respondent gave an assessment with a number 3, it meant that the respondent's perception was neutral, and if the respondent gave an answer at number 1, the respondent's perception was very negative to the question. The complete operational definition of variables can be seen in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Definition of Operational Variables

No	Variable	Definition	Indicator	Scale
1.	<i>Influencer marketing</i> (X1)	Kotler. According to Kevin and Chernev (2021, p. 318), influencer marketing refers to the use of popular online figures to promote products, services or brands within their social media feed	1. <i>Visibility</i> (Popularity) 2. <i>Credibility</i> 3. <i>Attractiveness</i> 4. <i>Power</i>	Interval
2.	<i>Online Customer Review</i> (X2)	Kotler, Kevin and Chernev (2021, p. 319), customer reviews can be very influential in creating customer preferences and purchasing decisions.	5. <i>Motivation</i> 6. <i>Source</i> 7. <i>Content</i>	Interval
3.	<i>Online Customer Rating</i> (X3)	Megawati (2019, p. 78), a rating is a consumer's opinion on a certain scale, a popular rating scheme for ratings in online stores is by giving a star rating.	5. <i>Credible</i> 6. <i>Expertise</i> 7. <i>Likable</i>	Interval
4.	<i>Purchase Interest</i> (Y)	Kotler and Keller (2021, p. 5), a purchase intention is consumer behavior that arises in response to objects that indicate a person's desire to make a purchase.	1. <i>Transactional interest</i> 2. <i>Referential interest</i> 3. <i>Preferential interest</i> 4. <i>Exploratory interest</i>	Interval

In this study, the validity test was carried out using a method by comparing the calculated r value with the r table value for degree of freedom (df) = $n-2$, in this case n is the number of samples. According to Mokodompit et al.

(2022, p. 980), reliability is a measurement result that can be trusted or must be reliable in the sense that it must have a level of consistency and stability.

3. Results

The characteristics of respondents based on the age of 150 respondents are 117 people (78%) aged 17 - 23 years, 33 people (22%) aged 24 - 30 years, and 0 people (0%) aged > 31 years. It can be concluded that the characteristics of respondents based on the most dominant age as users of the TikTok application and have or are still shopping at TikTok Shop, namely ages 17-23 years. This is due to the distribution of questionnaires to WhatsApp groups and friends of Gunadarma University, the majority of whom are aged 17-23 years.

The characteristics of respondents based on the occupation of 150 respondents are 116 people (72%) as students, 26 people (17%) as private / public employees, 6 people (4%) choose others, and 2 people (1%) as entrepreneurs. It can be concluded that the characteristics of respondents based on the most dominant occupation as users of the TikTok application and have or are still shopping at TikTok Shop, namely students. This is due to the distribution of questionnaires to WhatsApp groups and friends of Gunadarma University, the majority of whom are students. The characteristics of respondents based on income from 150 respondents are 73 people (49%) have an income of < Rp.1,000,000, 45 people (30%) have an income of Rp.1,000,000 - Rp.3,000,000, 26 people (17%) have an income of > Rp.5,000,000, and 6 people (4%) have an income of Rp.3,000,000 - Rp.5,000,000. The results can be explained that the questionnaire was distributed to whatsapp groups and friends of Gunadarma University who on average have an income or pocket money of less than Rp. 1,000,000.00.

The next stage is that the data that have been obtained are then classified by using the average score of the respondents' answers into five categories, namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. According to Azwar (2021, p. 159), the categorization will be carried out on each variable using the formula presented in the following Table 2.

Table 2: Categorization Norms

Categorization Norms	Categorization
$X \geq M + 1,5 SD$	Strongly agree
$M + 0,5 SD < X \leq M + 1,5 SD$	Agree
$M - 0,5 SD < X \leq M + 0,5 SD$	Neutral
$M - 1,5 SD < X \leq M - 0,5 SD$	Disagree
$X \leq M - 1,5 SD$	Strongly disagree

Description: X = Total Score; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

Based on the result of the calculation, on the influencer marketing variable, out of 150 respondents, 51.3% agreed and 30% strongly agreed. This shows that the most respondents' response to the influencer marketing variable is 51.3% which is in the "agree" column, meaning that the influencer marketing variable gets a positive response from respondents. The results of the calculation of the online customer review variable show that of the 150 respondents, 96.7% strongly agreed and 2.7% agreed. This shows that the most respondents' response to the online customer review variable is 96.7% which is in the "strongly agree" column, it means that the online customer review variable gets a positive response from respondents. The results of the calculation of the online customer rating variable in the table can be concluded that of the 150 respondents, 92.7% strongly agreed and 4% agreed. This shows that the most respondents' response to the online customer rating variable is 92.7% which is in the "strongly agree" column, meaning that the online customer rating variable gets a positive response from respondents.

Finally, the results of the calculation of the purchase interest variable in the table can be concluded that of the 150 respondents, 96% strongly agreed and 3.3% agreed. This shows that the most respondents' response to the purchase interest variable is 96% which is in the "strongly agree" column, it means that the purchase interest variable received a positive response from the respondents.

The stages of validity and reliability testing begin by testing as many as 30 respondents. After all the statements are valid and reliable, the distribution of the questionnaire is continued until the desired target is met, namely as many as 150 respondents.

Table 3: The Result of Validity Test of 150 Respondents

Variable of	R Count	R table	Description
<i>Influencer Marketing (X1)</i>			
X1.1	0,709	0,159	VALID
X1.2	0,885	0,159	VALID
X1.3	0,833	0,159	VALID
X1.4	0,784	0,159	VALID
X1.5	0,732	0,159	VALID
X2.2	0,710	0,159	VALID
X2.3	0,643	0,159	VALID
X2.4	0,698	0,159	VALID
<i>Online Customer Review (X2)</i>			
X2.1	0,661	0,159	VALID
X2.5	0,714	0,159	VALID
<i>Online Customer Rating (X3)</i>			
X3.1	0,736	0,159	VALID
X3.2	0,779	0,159	VALID
X3.3	0,644	0,159	VALID
X3.4	0,750	0,159	VALID
X3.5	0,712	0,159	VALID
<i>Purchasing Interest (Y)</i>			
Y.1	0,705	0,159	VALID
Y.2	0,722	0,159	VALID
Y.3	0,658	0,159	VALID
Y.4	0,774	0,159	VALID
Y.5	0,708	0,159	VALID

Table 4: The Result of Reliability Test of 150 Respondents

The Result of Reliability of 150 Respondents			
Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Reliable Value	Description
<i>Influencer Marketing (X1)</i>	0.844	0,70	Reliable
<i>Online Customer Review (X2)</i>	0,716	0,70	Reliable
<i>Online Customer Rating (X3)</i>	0,773	0,70	Reliable
<i>Purchasing Interest (Y)</i>	0,758	0,70	Reliable

Classical Assumption Test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results show the significance value of Asmp.Sig. (2-tailed) on the data is 0.200 > 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Heteroscedasticity testing using the glejser test.

Based on the results of the glejser test, it shows that the influencer marketing variable value has a significance value of 0.506, the online customer review variable has a significance value of 0.891, and the online customer rating variable has a significance value of 0.191. It can be concluded that the influencer marketing, online customer review, and online customer rating variables do not occur symptoms of heteroscedasticity because they have a value above 0.05 or 5%. Each independent variable, namely influencer marketing, online customer review, and online customer rating, has a tolerance value > 0.1 and a VIF value < 10. It can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in this study.

The next step after the classical assumption test is to ensure that the variables that have been selected are suitable for inclusion in the research model. This determination is made by conducting an F test first. The F test results show that the calculated F value is 29.021 and the F table value is 2.67. The significance value is 0.000. This means that the value of F count > F table (29.021 > 2.67) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level (0.000 < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected, and H_a is accepted. Thus it can be interpreted that this research model is feasible to use because there is an influence between influencer marketing, online customer reviews, and online customer ratings on buying interest in the TikTok Shop application simultaneously.

Table 5: Test Result T

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance VIF
1	(Constant)	3.248	2.035		1.596	.113	
	X1	.103	.052	.132	1.990	.048	.970 1.030
	X2	.588	.075	.526	7.835	.000	.953 1.050
	X3	.163	.064	.172	2.526	.013	.925 1.081

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The results of hypothesis testing for the influencer marketing variable (X1) show that the t value is 1.990 and the t table value is 1.655, as seen in Table 5. This means that the value of t count > t table (1.990 > 1.655) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level (0.048 < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected, H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is an influence between influencer marketing variables on customer buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. In this study, the influencer marketing variable has an effect on buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. This is supported by the results of respondents' responses agreeing that being an influencer must be reliable in promoting products, so that individuals imitate what is displayed. The results of hypothesis testing for the online customer review variable (X2) show that the t value is 7.835 and the t table value is 1.655. This means that the value of t count > t table (7.835 > 1.655) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level (0.000 < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected, H_a is accepted. Therefore it can be concluded that there is an influence between the online customer review variable on customer buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. In this study, the online customer review variable has an effect on buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. This is supported by the results of respondents' responses strongly agreeing that the more the number of positive reviews, the better the product's reputation.

The results of hypothesis testing for the online customer rating variable (X3) show that the t value is 2.526 and the t table value is 1.655. This means that the value of t count > t table (2.526 > 1.655) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level (0.013 < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected, H_a is accepted. Therefore it can be concluded that there is an influence between the online customer rating variable on customer buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. This is supported by the results of respondents' responses strongly agreeing that ratings have a direct influence in finding the product information needed.

$$\text{Purchasing Interest} = 3,248 + 0,103 \text{ IM} + 0,588 \text{ Re} + 0,163 \text{ Ra}$$

The test results can show that there are three independent variables, namely influencer marketing, online customer reviews, and online customer ratings. The highest coefficient value of them is the online customer review variable, that is 0.588. It can be said that the online customer review variable has a more dominant influence on purchase intention. According to Ghazali (2018) if the regression coefficient value of the independent variable on the dependent variable has the largest value, then the independent variable has a dominant influence.

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination test, it shows that the coefficient of determination (Adjusted R Square) is 0.361 or 36.1%. This means that 36.1% of purchasing interest can be explained by influencer marketing variables (X1), online customer review variables (X2), and online customer rating variables (X3). The remaining 63.9% is influenced by other variables not explained in this study such as price, product quality, brand image, and others.

4. Discussion

The influencer marketing has a lot of fans (popular aspect) and can make it like an advertisement so that it easily gets attention (credible aspect). An influencer can attract individuals or groups of advertised products (attractiveness aspect), is also reliable in promoting products so that individuals or groups follow or imitate what is shown (strength aspect). The results of this study are in line with Arief, et.al (2023), Agustin and Amron (2022) and Iffah and Farouk (2022) that influencer marketing affects a person's buying interest in a product. The results of research conducted based on questionnaires filled out by respondents stated that the online customer review variable on buying interest in the TikTok Shop application is classified as good with an average of 96.7% from several statements such as the more the number of positive reviews, the better the product's reputation, getting benefits from online customer reviews, and positive review results affect the opinion of the product.

Online customer reviews affect purchasing interest in the TikTok Shop application. Statistically, it can be seen that the effect on buying interest is because the t value is obtained at 7.835 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. The existence of this influence indicates that the better the online customer review, the more buying interest will increase. Vice versa, the worse the online customer review, the more buying interest will decrease. The consumers benefit from online customer reviews. Because a positive review will influence someone's opinion of the product (awareness aspect). Reviews of an e-commerce product will provide information about the advantages and disadvantages of the product (frequency aspect).

The number of positive online customer reviews indicates that the store is trusted. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Lackermair et.al (2013), Arief, et.al (2023), Harli, Mutasowifin, and Andrianto (2021) that online consumer reviews have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Thus, sellers should ask consumers to write honest and true reviews in order to create interest in buying the next consumer.

The online customer rating affects purchasing interest in the TikTok Shop application. The existence of this influence indicates that the better the online customer rating, the more buying interest will increase. Vice versa, the worse the online customer rating, the more buying interest will decrease. Ratings increase the effectiveness of online shopping (credible aspect) and have a direct influence in finding the product information needed (expertise aspect). The existence of a rating can also convince the choice (expertise aspect) and make the person selling the product happy because people can trust and choose the desired product (fun aspect). The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Oryza et.al (2022), and Komariyah (2022) that ratings have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion conducted it can be concluded that influencer marketing, online customer reviews, online customer ratings affect buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. The results of this study prove that the influencer marketing, online customer reviews, and online customer ratings are among the variables that determine buying interest in the TikTok Shop application. The research implications are as

follows: TikTok application users consider that being an influencer must be reliable in promoting products, the more the number of positive reviews, the better the product's reputation. Furthermore, the ratings also have a direct influence in finding the product information needed.

The suggestions of this research are: the sellers / companies must be able to maintain and improve influencer marketing, online customer reviews, and online customer ratings that are very good considered by the TikTok users so that the users choose to purchase their needs and are willing to recommend TikTok Shop to the closest people. For further research, it is hoped that this research can be a reference for the future and there are still other factors that influence purchasing interest. It is expected that this research can be continued by other researchers by adding other variables such as price, brand image and product quality, so that the research becomes better and more complete.

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